

Elektr energiyasini boshqarish jarayonlarini raqamlashtirish va avtomatlashtirish

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Dolzarbliigi: elektr energiyasini boshqarish jarayonlarini raqam-lashtirish va avtomatlashtirish masalasi bugungi kunning dolzarb masalalaridan hisoblanadi. Ushbu jarayonda ma'lumotlarni o'zaro almashinish jarayonlarini nazorat qilish, ma'lumotlarni ishonchligini ta'minlash raqamlashtirishning asosiy vazifasi hisoblanib, ushbu maqolada elektr energiya iste'moli va samaradorligini tahlil qilishda ma'lumotlarning aniq va ishonchli bo'lishini ta'minlash usuli va algoritmlari tahlil etilgan. Maqolada ma'lumotlarni qabul qilish, qayta ishlash va saqlash jarayonlarini standartlashtirish va ularni mantiqiy, dinamik va statistik tekshirish asosida modellashtirish bo'yicha asosiy yo'nalishlar keltirilgan.

Maqsad: ushbu maqolada elektr energiyasini boshqarish jarayonlarini raqamlashtirish va avtomatlashtirishni tashkil etish va unda ma'lumotlarning o'zaro almashinuvi, ishonchligini ta'minlash usuli va algoritmlarini ishlab chiqish asosiy maqsad qilib belgilab olindi.

Usullari: dinamik va statistik tahlil, regression tahlil, mantiqiy analiz, ma'lumotlarni xalqaro birliklarga moslashtirish.

Natijalar: elektr energiyasini boshqarish jarayonlarini raqamlashtirish va avtomatlashtirish energetika boshqaruv tizimi uchun aniq va ishonchli ma'lumotlar almashinuvi ta'minlangandagina to'g'ri va aniq natija beradi. Shu bilan birga, maqolada elektr energiyasini boshqarish jarayonlarini raqamlashtirish va avtomatlashtirishda ma'lumotlar almashinuvi ishonchligini ta'minlash usuli va algoritmlari ishlab chiqilgan bo'lib, bu energiya iste'molini samarali tahlil qilish va boshqarish imkon beradi.

Kalit so'zlari: energetika boshqaruv tizimi, ma'lumotlar bazasi, energiya iste'moli, Gauss taqsimoti, mantiqiy tekshiruv, chiziqli regressiya, xalqaro birliklar sistemasiga muvofiqlik, energiya samaradorligi, ma'lumotlar tahlili, energiya boshqaruvi.

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Автоматизация процессов управления электропотреблением на основе цифровизация

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Актуальность: цифровизация и автоматизация процессов управления электрической энергией являются актуальными задачами сегодняшнего дня. Они включают, в первую очередь, контроль обмена данными и обеспечение их надежности. В данной статье проанализированы методы и алгоритмы, обеспечивающие точность и надежность данных, используемых при анализе объемов и эффективности потребления электрической энергии. Основное внимание в статье уделено стандартизации, логической, динамической и статистической проверке процессов приема, обработки и хранения данных.

Цель: Основной целью данной статьи является разработка методов и алгоритмов для организации цифровизации и автоматизации процессов управления электрической энергией, включая обмен данными и обеспечение их надежности.

Методы: динамический и статистический анализ, регрессионный анализ, логический анализ, адаптация данных к международным стандартам.

Результаты: разработаны методы и алгоритмы, обеспечивающие надежный обмен данными, что позволяет эффективно анализировать и управлять потреблением электроэнергии. Они основаны на цифровизации и автоматизации, которые позволяют оперировать с достоверными результатами и обеспечивают надежный обмен данными.

Ключевые слова: система управления энергетикой, база данных, потребление энергии, распределение Гаусса, логическая проверка, линейная регрессия, соответствие международной системе единиц, энергоэффективность, анализ данных, управление энергией.

Digitization and automation of power management processes

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Relevance: the digitalization and automation of electricity management processes are critical issues today. In this process, the main objectives of digitalization are to control data exchange and ensure data reliability. This article analyzes the methods and algorithms that ensure data accuracy and reliability in analyzing electricity consumption and efficiency. Key directions are presented for standardizing data reception, processing, and storage processes and for modeling them based on logical, dynamic, and statistical verification.

Aim: the main goal of this article is to develop methods and algorithms for organizing the digitalization and automation of electricity management processes, including data exchange and reliability assurance.

Methods: dynamic and statistical analysis, regression analysis, logical analysis, adaptation of data to international standards.

Results: The results of the article indicate that an accurate and reliable database for the energy management system has been developed, enabling efficient analysis and management of energy consumption. Verification of data against the Gaussian distribution and logical checks ensure data accuracy, enhancing its effective use. A module was also developed to ensure compliance with the international system of units, facilitating data processing and analysis. Regression analysis revealed relationships between data points, assisting in identifying ways to improve energy efficiency.

Key words: The digitalization and automation of electricity management processes provide accurate and reliable results for energy management systems only when reliable data exchange is ensured. The article presents developed methods and algorithms to ensure reliable data exchange, enabling efficient energy consumption analysis and management.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the global energy sector has experienced a significant shift towards digitalization and automation to meet increasing demands for efficiency, sustainability, and environmental responsibility. Energy management systems play a vital role in enabling organizations to monitor, analyze, and optimize energy consumption. Accurate and reliable data is critical to these systems, as it informs decision-making processes and supports the goals of reducing energy waste, enhancing operational efficiency, and minimizing environmental impacts. The importance of quality data in energy management lies not only in its ability to improve operational practices but also in its potential to guide the strategic use of energy resources [1,2]. Inaccuracies or inconsistencies in energy consumption data can lead to poor resource allocation, increased costs, and suboptimal energy use. Therefore, establish-

ing a standardized and robust data collection, processing, and storage framework is crucial for achieving high-quality data analytics. This paper addresses the challenges and methodologies associated with the digital transformation of energy management processes. It proposes a comprehensive approach to managing energy consumption data that combines statistical techniques, such as Gaussian distribution analysis and regression analysis, with logical verification. These techniques ensure the accuracy, consistency, and reliability of data, facilitating effective decision-making in energy management systems. Furthermore, the study incorporates a module for standardizing data into international units, enhancing data interoperability and usability [3,4].

The primary objectives of this research are to develop reliable methods for data verification and modeling, create a standardized data framework for energy management systems, and ultimately support efficient energy resource utilization, cost reduction, and minimized environmental impact [5]. By presenting a structured approach to data management, this study contributes to the evolving field of energy management and offers practical tools for organizations aiming to improve energy efficiency and sustainability through data-driven decision-making.

2. Methods and materials

This study employs a range of statistical, logical, and computational methods to enhance the accuracy and reliability of energy consumption data within energy management systems (EMS). Data collection involved gathering energy metrics such as electricity, water, and heat usage from EMS-integrated meters and manual records. These datasets were categorized by resource type, device, and environmental condition, then organized within a structured database framework to ensure easy retrieval and systematic analysis. Additionally, a unit conversion module was developed to standardize all data to international measurement units (SI units), allowing for uniform calculations across varied energy data types and improving interoperability within the EMS [6].

To verify data accuracy, the study utilized Gaussian distribution analysis for statistical validation, calculating skewness (g_1) and kurtosis (g_2) coefficients to detect anomalies in data distribution. Data outside expected distribution parameters were flagged as potential outliers. Logical verification algorithms further supported data integrity by applying thresholds to acceptable data ranges, thus identifying errors due to human or mechanical factors. Linear regression analysis was also used to assess correlations among variables, such as energy input and output, enhancing confidence in data trends. These statistical and logical checks were embedded into a set of algorithms, developed in Python using libraries like NumPy and Pandas, to automate data handling, error detection, and unit conversion. Tested on a 2022 dataset, these methods provided a reliable foundation for precise energy data management, supporting operational optimization within EMS.

3. Results and Discussion

The database serves as the core component for executing all operations within digital systems [7; 15, pp. 139-153; 8]. For accurate analysis of energy consumption, it is essential to establish clearly defined cells for the data presented to digital systems. Additionally, data entry must be user-friendly, straightforward, and comprehensive, covering all types of resources and services [9; pp. 74-88; 40; pp. 1-32; 10; pp. 967-972; 11; pp. 279-289]. In digital systems, the initial step in analyzing energy consumption involves linking essential energy resources, products, and service types to functions in the settings section.

The digital system's database is structured to categorize the data entered into distinct groups:

- Data identification: Information that records the location and time of the entered data.
- User activity-related data: Information associated with energy resources/products/services and the specified normative parameters.
- Data on primary and auxiliary equipment: Parameters of all types of equipment.
- Weather and work schedules: Information regarding weather conditions and working hours.

The data intake process involves verifying the accuracy of initial data and ensuring logical sequence alignment by integrating newly entered data with previously recorded entries. This results in a consolidated time series dataset, X , for which skewness (g_1) and kurtosis (g_2) coefficients are calculated to assess data distribution and symmetry.

$$g_1 = \frac{n}{(n-1)(n-2)} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i - \mu}{\sigma} \right)^3 \quad (1)$$

$$g_2 = \frac{n(n+1)}{(n-1)(n-2)(n-3)} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i - \mu}{\sigma} \right)^4 - \frac{3(n-1)^2}{(n-2)(n-3)} \quad (2)$$

where, μ - represents the mean value of the X dataset, and σ is the standard deviation of the X dataset.

It is known that when $g_1 = 0$ and $g_2 = 3$, the new data entered will align with the previously entered values. Considering deviations beyond the standard range of initially entered data, the deviation coefficient θ is calculated as follows:

$$\theta = \frac{\sigma}{\mu} \tag{3}$$

If $\mu = \frac{1}{N} \sum x_i$ and $\sigma = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum (x_i - \mu)$:

$$\theta = \frac{N}{N-1} \sum 1 - \frac{\sum x_i}{N \cdot x_i} \tag{4}$$

Taking θ into account, all new incoming values are checked against the following negation and conjunction logical expression B :

$$B = \neg(g_1(1 - \theta) < x_N \wedge g_1(1 + \theta) > x_N \wedge \wedge g_2(1 - \theta) < x_N \wedge g_2(1 + \theta) > x_N) \tag{5}$$

If $B = \text{true}$, a notification is generated indicating that the newly entered data in the digital systems contains an error; otherwise, the data is accepted as correct. During the research, data from Copper Enrichment Plant (CEP)-2's production workshops and plants for 2022 were used to test the developed modules in trial mode.

Digital systems unit handling module. The unit of entered data is considered its primary element. To ensure that the units of data entered into the digital system are correctly interpreted, a unit-handling module was developed. This module saves all entered data in the database in terms of the base units of the International System of Units (SI). For example, when entering electrical energy consumption for CEP-2 as 79.8 thousand kWh, the system divides this value by four to store it in the database as follows:

- Core data: 79.8
- Magnitude: Thousand
- Unit and its SI representation: 1 kWh = 3600 W·s
- Value in other units: e.g., TOE (tons of oil equivalent), kcal, GJ.

Additionally, energy values entered can be converted into any desired unit according to SI standards, based on a universal unit conversion diagram [12]. Here, conversion coefficients are compiled into a matrix K in a specific order and stored in the database. Any energy form can be converted from one unit to another using the following expression:

$$\vartheta_i = K_{ij} \vartheta_j \tag{6}$$

This allows the digital system database to store entered data, convert it into any desired format, and generate reports in convenient units.

Method and algorithm for processing data entered into the digital system database. The digital system accepts data in two formats:

- Through integration from the database of electronic meters.
- By manual entry from operators into the digital system.

Fig.1. Data Processing Algorithm for the Digital System Database

In both cases, errors may be recorded in the data accepted into the digital system database. In the first case, errors may arise from meter malfunctions, while in the second case, they may result from human error.

To account for both situations, a data verification algorithm was developed. This algorithm

performs checks on randomly selected values based on the Gaussian distribution (Figure 1):

$$P(t) = \frac{1}{\sigma \cdot \sqrt{2 \cdot \pi}} \cdot e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{t-\mu}{\sigma} \right)^2} \quad (7)$$

where, $\mu = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^N x_i$ – the mean (arithmetic average) of the time series data. $\sigma^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^N (x_i - \mu)^2}{N}$ – deviation from the mean (standard deviation) of the values. Considering Bessel's correction, the standard deviation is calculated as follows [13, 14]:

$$s^2 = \frac{N-1}{N} \sigma^2 \quad (8)$$

Next, the z-value is determined. This z-value indicates how far each time series data point deviates from its mean (arithmetic average):

$$z = \frac{x - \mu}{s} \quad (9)$$

If the values are the result of a specific process and have minimal errors, $z_{\max}$ and $z_{\min}$ will converge, and their sum will approach zero. When $z_{\max} + z_{\min} > 2$, the degree of deviation increases, and using these values in analysis may lead to errors. According to Figure 1, when $z_{\max} + z_{\min} > 2$, a "false" value is returned, and this result is used as an indicator in the digital system database to trigger data revalidation. Otherwise, a "true" value is assigned, and the data proceeds to the next processing step.

Additionally, among the accepted data, the proportional relationship between the data in sections ϕ_2 and ϕ_3 is checked. Accordingly, if linear regression analysis, given by $Y = ax + b$, yields a coefficient a greater than zero, it confirms that the values are logically correct. This coefficient is calculated as follows (Figure 2):

$$a = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{n(\sum x^2) - (\sum x)^2} \quad (10)$$

where, n – represents the number of data points involved in the analysis, and x and y correspond to the data from sections ϕ_2 and ϕ_3 , respectively.

Fig.2. Algorithm for linear regression analysis of ϕ_2 and ϕ_3 data

If the entered data is correct, the system returns a "true" value; otherwise, it returns a "false" value.

These values are used as indicators in the database to denote data reliability.

Modeling, Processing, and Evaluation of CEP-2 Data in Digital Systems. To properly analyze energy consumption and accurately calculate energy efficiency in subsequent stages, it is essential to correctly model CEP-2 in digital systems. This involves verifying the initial data in two stages, based on the Gaussian distribution law and logical conditions.

Fig. 3. Technological Process of the CEP-2

Figure 3 presents the stages of the copper-molybdenum ore enrichment technology at MBF-2, based on which the structure for recording the plant's electricity consumption data is organized, as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Structuring Primary Data of the Technological Process of MBF-2 in Digital Systems (note: abbreviations are name of part of the workshops)

To perform analyses within digital systems, the data structure outlined in Figure 4 was used to input the information provided in Section 2.2 of the dissertation. Specifically, based on item 2.2 in Section 2.2 of the dissertation, the following data were entered into the digital system's database:

- Electricity consumption (thousand kWh) and its set norms (thousand kWh/ton),
- Water consumption (thousand m³) and its set norms (thousand m³/ton),
- Heat energy consumption (thousand kcal) and its set norms (thousand kcal/ton),
- Processed raw material quantities (tons).

The data entered into the digital system's database were then processed. Initially, all entered data were checked against the Gaussian distribution. The electricity consumption and copper-molybdenum ore quantities were verified according to the Gaussian distribution, as shown in Figure 5.

The results of this check, as illustrated in Figure 5, indicate that the condition $z_{\max} + z_{\min} < 1.4$ for electricity consumption and $z_{\max} + z_{\min} < 0.67$ for copper-molybdenum ore quantity were satisfied, thus meeting the specified criteria.

Fig. 5. Results of Processing Initial Data on MBF-2 Electricity Consumption a) Electricity Consumption, b) Processed Copper-Molybdenum Ore Quantity

In the next stage, the initial data entered into the digital system's database are checked based on logical conditions and undergo regression analysis, with the linear regression coefficient calculated (Figure 6). The linear regression coefficient was found to be $a = 0.3235$, satisfying the condition $a > 0$.

Fig. 6. Verification of Logical Proportionality Condition between MBF-2 Electricity Consumption and Copper-Molybdenum Ore Quantity

The data entered were verified based on both the Gaussian distribution law and logical conditions. The results indicate that the data meet the specified criteria, allowing them to be used in subsequent stages.

4. Conclusion

This study has demonstrated the importance of accurate and reliable data management within energy management systems for efficient and effective energy consumption analysis. Through the inte-

gration of statistical and logical validation methods, such as Gaussian distribution analysis and regression analysis, the data entered into the system were verified for accuracy and consistency. The unit conversion module further ensured uniformity by standardizing all data to international units, facilitating better interoperability within the system.

The developed algorithms for data validation, logical checks, and regression analysis provide a solid foundation for reliable data processing in digital systems, particularly in complex industrial settings like the Copper Enrichment Plant. By meeting the specified criteria, the system can now process data with a high degree of accuracy, allowing for effective monitoring and optimization of energy consumption. Ultimately, this approach contributes to reducing operational costs, improving energy efficiency, and minimizing environmental impact, marking a significant step forward in the digital transformation of energy management practices.

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